

Task 4.2A (subtask 1): Implement visual and performance enhancements in BioPortal's ontology term viewer for terms used in the RADx Data Hub

Technical Report

Owner: Stanford University

Revision History

Date (YYYY-MM-DD)	Version Number	Revision Reviewed / Approved By	Brief Description of Change
2024-12-10	v1	Document created by Michael Dorf (mdorf@stanford.edu) from the Stanford University Team.	Document created
2025-01-15	v1.1	Document written by Michael Dorf (mdorf@stanford.edu) from the Stanford University Team.	First draft completed
2025-01-23	v2.0	Marcos Martínez-Romero (marcosmr@stanford.edu)	Revised and commented
2025-01-24	v2.1	Michael Dorf (mdorf@stanford.edu)	Corrected based on Marcos Martínez Romero feedback
2025-02-26	v2.2	Michael Dorf (mdorf@stanford.edu) Marcos Martínez-Romero (marcosmr@stanford.edu)	Revised based on NIH feedback

Purpose

The RADx Data Hub integrates BioPortal's biomedical ontologies to enhance the clarity and consistency of metadata for studies and data files. By adopting BioPortal's standardized terms, the RADx Data Hub enhances accuracy and interoperability of study data, making it easier to share and analyze these data across various studies. Task 4.2A aims to develop enhancements to the BioPortal [1,2] term display to facilitate ontology discovery, improve understanding of ontology terms, and promote the reuse of ontologies and terms by the RADx research community and the broader scientific community. Subtask 1 (or 4.2A-1) focuses on several visual and performance enhancements in BioPortal's ontology term viewer to allow for a better user experience when working with the terms used in the RADx Data Hub. This report outlines the technical work and software developed to date to achieve these goals.

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Introduction

The RADx Data Hub leverages BioPortal's comprehensive biomedical ontologies to standardize and present consistent metadata across its diverse studies. For RADx researchers and users, the accessibility of an established resource like BioPortal is crucial, not only for ensuring metadata uniformity but also for enhancing the ease with which data can be navigated and utilized. Every time an ontology is updated, the RADx Data Hub team must ensure that the associated links to BioPortal ontology terms remain functional. To maintain the integrity of the metadata, these links require periodic verification. Should any discrepancies arise, the metadata must be promptly corrected to ensure continuous accuracy and accessibility.

The user-friendly display of BioPortal's terms is essential for the effective use of RADx Data Hub resources, allowing researchers to quickly find and apply the correct ontological terms. Prior to these improvements, BioPortal's term display suffered from several limitations, including an inability to properly highlight the desired term in its tree context, an inability to scroll the term tree independently of the term details pane, and a dated, user-unfriendly presentation of term details.

Task 4.2A-1 focuses on enhancing the display of the RADx Data Hub relevant ontology terms in BioPortal to facilitate easier browsing and navigation. As part of this initiative, the Stanford team has updated the BioPortal user interface's architecture, phasing out older technologies like jQuery in favor of more contemporary choices such as the Turbo library, the Stimulus JavaScript framework, and the ViewComponent framework, which allows building reusable, testable & encapsulated presentation components in Ruby on Rails. This effort further aligns our codebase with the OntoPortal Alliance [3], making future enhancements to RADx Data Hub's BioPortal artifacts more easily accomplished.

The recent updates required an additional upfront investment of time to refresh BioPortal libraries and realign the codebase with the standards set by the OntoPortal Alliance. This endeavor, though resource-intensive, will facilitate future upgrades. By adopting the most current technologies, we anticipate long-term benefits in efficiency and performance.

In addition to these backend improvements, the Stanford team has introduced several new user interface (UI) features specifically designed to overcome the aforementioned limitations. These enhancements include:

1. **Enhanced Navigation:** The UI is now capable of navigating to and selecting the term regardless of its position in the hierarchical tree, making the term view much more user-friendly.
2. **Independent Scrolling:** The term tree and detail views now feature independent scrolling. This allows users to peruse the term tree without losing sight of the details they are reviewing, improving navigation and readability.
3. **Improved Term Detail View:** The term detail view has been revamped to prioritize the most relevant information at the top. Additionally, term properties are now presented in a more intuitive and compact multi-value format, simplifying the visual presentation and making it easier to digest multiple properties at a glance.

The following sections describe these improvements in detail.

BioPortal architecture upgrade

In the latest update to BioPortal, the Stanford team addressed the outdated components of BioPortal's user interface architecture. Previously, the platform relied on defunct technologies like jQuery and SimpleTree, which had lost support from the open-source community. These outdated libraries have been replaced with modern Ruby on Rails compatible alternatives. Now, Hotwire Turbo takes charge of managing HTML requests to the server and handling the responses, enhancing the efficiency and responsiveness of BioPortal. Additionally, for interactions that Turbo cannot handle, the Stanford team has integrated Stimulus—a minimalist JavaScript framework—to ensure smooth and effective user interactions. This overhaul not only modernizes BioPortal's platform but also aligns it with current web standards and practices.

The Turbo captures all link clicks and form submissions, and extracts the body from the response in order to replace it in the existing page. It works by extracting the body from the server's response and seamlessly replacing it in the existing page, allowing for updates to individual sections without the need for a full page reload. Behind the scenes, it also performs actions that keep the browser back button working properly (Figure 1).

Figure 1: The Turbo library partial page update.

Figure 1 depicts the partial page update feature of the Turbo library. Instead of reloading the entire page, Turbo takes the HTML response from the server and replaces only the relevant parts of the original page—specifically, the Body section as indicated in the figure.

Stimulus is a modern JavaScript framework that's designed to augment the BioPortal UI HTML with just the minimalist behavior to support the needed functionality. Stimulus pairs well with Turbo to provide a complete solution for fast, compelling and user-friendly BioPortal user experience.

To facilitate the reuse of functionality developed by other OntoPortal Alliance members, the ViewComponent framework was integrated into the BioPortal architecture. These custom components are designed to implement a specific piece of functionality and can be seamlessly dropped into any page. A library of already developed UI components exists both in the open source community and in the other Alliance members repositories. These can now be utilized by the BioPortal user interface.

Auto-select and scroll to the selected term

When a user clicks on the “Visualize Metadata File” for a particular study on the RADx website, one of the properties presented is the “Subject Identifier”, which includes a link to the corresponding term in BioPortal (refer to Figure 2 below). For larger ontologies, such as Medical Subject Headings (MeSH), the term in question may be deeply nested within the term tree, requiring extensive expansion. Prior to this recent update, the desired term was not automatically selected or navigated to within BioPortal after clicking the metadata link in RADx, which often led to user confusion.

Figure 2: RADx Data Hub Study Overview and Metadata Viewer.

Figure 2 displays a fragment of the overview page for the study with dbGaP accession phs002660 (accessible at <https://radxdatahub.nih.gov/study/101>) and highlights the icon for viewing metadata using the RADx Data Hub Metadata Viewer. The Metadata Viewer provides a link to the COVID-19 term from the Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) in BioPortal. The user interface in the original BioPortal did not explicitly navigate to the selected term in the tree (Figure 3). For larger ontologies, such as MeSH, deeply nested terms, though highlighted, often appeared off-screen, creating confusion for the user.

The screenshot shows the BioPortal interface for Medical Subject Headings. The left sidebar contains a tree of categories, with 'Amino Acids, Peptides, and Proteins' highlighted in a red box. The main area shows the 'Details' pane for 'COVID-19', which is also highlighted in a red box. A red arrow points from the 'COVID-19' term in the details pane to the 'Amino Acids, Peptides, and Proteins' category in the tree.

Medical Subject Headings
Last updated: August 28, 2024

Summary **Classes** Properties Notes Mappings Widgets

Jump to:

Details Visualization Notes (0) Class Mappings (47)

Preferred Name **COVID-19**

SARS CoV 2 Infection
Coronavirus Disease 2019
Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2 Infection
COVID 19 Virus Infection
Infection, 2019-nCoV
2019-nCoV Infection
COVID-19 Virus Diseases
COVID 19 Virus Disease
2019 Novel Coronavirus Disease
Coronavirus Disease-19
Coronavirus Disease 19
COVID19
Disease, COVID-19 Virus
Infection, SARS-CoV-2
SARS Coronavirus 2 Infection
COVID-19 Pandemics
2019-nCoV Diseases
Pandemic, COVID-19
COVID-19 Virus Disease
COVID 19

Synonyms

Figure 3: Old behavior: “COVID-19” is the currently displayed term, as evident by the details pane on the right. However, it is not automatically selected and is not visible in the term tree on the left.

Figure 4 demonstrates the enhancement where the left side of the screen now automatically focuses on the precise location in the hierarchy where the term “COVID-19”, linked from the RADx data hub is located. This update eliminates the need for users to manually scroll through the hierarchy and visually identify the term, as it automatically finds and highlights the correct position.

Figure 4: New behavior: The term “COVID-19” is automatically highlighted and navigated to its precise location in the term tree on the left.

Independent scrolling between the concept tree and the details section

Prior to this update, the BioPortal term viewer was constrained to a single monolithic view that did not allow independent scrolling between the tree and the details sections of the ontology. As a result, users viewing a term with extensive properties had to scroll down the page, causing the term tree to disappear from view (Figure 5). Similarly, when a term deep within the tree was accessed, the details section would move out of view.

The term tree becomes hidden at the top as a result of the user scrolling down the page to see the term details

definition
A viral disorder generally characterized by high FEVER; COUGH; DYSPNEA; CHILLS; PERSISTENT TREMOR; MUSCLE PAIN; HEADACHE; SORE THROAT; a new loss of taste and/or smell (see AGEUSIA and ANOSMIA) and other symptoms of a VIRAL PNEUMONIA. In severe cases, a myriad of coagulopathy associated symptoms often correlating with COVID-19 severity is seen (e.g., BLOOD COAGULATION; THROMBOSIS; ACUTE RESPIRATORY DISTRESS SYNDROME; SEIZURES; HEART ATTACK; STROKE; multiple CEREBRAL INFARCTIONS; KIDNEY FAILURE; catastrophic ANTIPHOSPHOLIPID ANTIBODY SYNDROME and/or DISSEMINATED INTRAVASCULAR COAGULATION). In younger patients, rare inflammatory syndromes are sometimes associated with COVID-19 (e.g., atypical KAWASAKI SYNDROME; TOXIC SHOCK SYNDROME; pediatric multisystem inflammatory disease; and CYTOKINE STORM SYNDROME). A coronavirus, SARS-CoV-2, in the genus BETACORONAVIRUS is the causative agent.

DX	20210101
EC	drug therapy:COVID-19 Drug Treatment
FX	D000086402
HN	2021(2020)

- blood
- diet therapy
- diagnosis
- therapy
- immunology
- cerebrospinal fluid
- chemically induced
- history
- metabolism
- prevention & control
- veterinary
- parasitology
- congenital
- complications

Figure 5: Old Behavior: The tree on the left becomes hidden at the top when the user scrolls down to examine the term details.

Figure 5 shows the example of the old behavior that caused the term tree to be off screen when the user scrolled down to examine the term details. The new functionality allows users to independently scroll between the tree and the details panes (Figure 6).

Figure 6: New Behavior: The term tree on the left and the term details pane on the right now scroll independently, enabling users to review term properties without losing sight of the term's location in the tree.

Improved presentation of concept details

The concept details pane was completely re-written using the ViewComponent technology that allowed the most important concept information, such as the ID, Preferred Name, Synonyms and Definitions to be displayed at the top of the page (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Improved Details Pane: In BioPortal, all ontologies—whether originally in OBO, OWL, or RDF format—feature a set of core properties including ID, Preferred Name, Synonyms, and Definitions. These properties are now prominently grouped and displayed at the top of the term details pane for enhanced visibility and accessibility.

The display format for synonyms has been updated to a "badge" view (Figure 8), which highlights each synonym clearly and arranges them in a horizontal row. This new layout replaces the previous version, where synonyms were listed vertically, one per line, often extending the page length for terms with multiple synonyms. To keep the interface compact while still providing access to extended information, a "See more" link has been integrated, allowing users to expand the view as necessary. This enhancement improves both the aesthetics and the usability of our interface.

The screenshot shows the BioPortal interface for Medical Subject Headings. On the left, there is a 'Jump to:' search box and a tree view of classes. The 'COVID-19' class is selected. On the right, the 'Details' tab is active, showing the definition: 'PNEUMONIA. A coronavirus, SARS-CoV-2 VIRUS, in the genus BETACORONAVIRUS is the causative agent.' Below the definition, a list of synonyms is displayed in a compact 'badge' format. The synonyms are: SARS CoV 2 Infection, Coronavirus Disease 2019, Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2 Infection, COVID 19 Virus Infection, Infection, 2019-nCoV, 2019-nCoV Infection, COVID-19 Virus Diseases, COVID 19 Virus Disease, 2019 Novel Coronavirus Disease, and Coronavirus Disease-19. A 'See more' link is located at the bottom of the list. A red arrow points to the 'See more' link with the text 'Synonym "Badge" View with "See more" link'.

Figure 8: Synonyms are now displayed in a compact "badge" format, clearly delineating each value. To prevent the details display from being overwhelmed by terms with numerous synonyms, a "See more" link has been added. Users can view the full set of synonyms as needed by clicking this link.

The remaining concept properties have been consolidated into a section titled "All Properties." This section is designed to be expandable and contractible, ensuring the term display remains compact and navigable. Users can easily access a comprehensive view of all associated properties by expanding this section as needed (Figure 9). This approach provides a consistent presentation of terms across the various ontologies referenced by the RADx Data Hub. Researchers can quickly access essential details while retaining the option to explore deeper into ontology-specific properties where the term is defined.

The screenshot shows the BioPortal interface for Medical Subject Headings. The browser address bar shows the URL: `bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/MESH?p=classes&conceptid=http...`. The page title is "Medical Subject Headings" with a sub-header "Last uploaded: January 16, 2025". The navigation bar includes "Summary", "Classes", "Properties", "Notes", "Mappings", and "Widgets". The "Classes" tab is active, showing a tree view of classes. The "COVID-19" class is selected. The "Details" pane shows the following information:

- All Properties** (highlighted with a red box and arrow)
- definition**: A viral disorder generally characterized by high FEVER; COUGH; DYSPNEA; CHILLS; PERSISTENT TREMOR; MUSCLE PAIN; HEADACHE; SORE THROAT; a new loss of taste and/or smell (see AGEUSIA and ANOSMIA) and other symptoms of a VIRAL PNEUMONIA. A coronavirus, SARS-CoV-2 VIRUS, in the genus BETACORONAVIRUS is the causative agent.
- altLabel**: SARS CoV 2 Infection, Coronavirus Disease 2019, Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2 Infection, COVID 19 Virus Infection, Infection, 2019-nCoV. (See more)
- prefLabel**: COVID-19
- TH**: NLM (2020), NLM (2022), NLM (2021)

Figure 9: Improved Details Pane: All term properties unique to a specific ontology are now organized within an expandable and collapsible section titled "All Properties." This section allows users to toggle the information in or out of view with a simple click.

Resources

This section contains links to the source code developed as part of this task.

Github Repositories

- https://github.com/ncbo/bioportal_web_ui
- https://github.com/ontportal/ontportal_web_ui

- https://github.com/ontoportallirmm/bioportal_web_ui

Issue Tracking

- [Implement enhancements to BioPortal's ontology term viewer for terms used in the RADx Data Hub](#)
- [AgroPortal and BioPortal code base alignment](#)
- [Feature: Align Bioportal and AgroPortal - part 1 - Configuration code and Docker](#)
- [Feature: Align Bioportal and AgroPortal - part 2.1 - Add UI tests](#)
- [Feature: Align Bioportal and AgroPortal - part 2.2 - Add some view components](#)
- [Feature: Align Bioportal and AgroPortal - part 3 - Update ontology viewer to Turbo](#)
- [Feature: Align Bioportal and AgroPortal - part 4 - Independent scrolling and Concept tree autoscroll to selected node and UI bug fixes](#)
- [Feature: Align Bioportal and AgroPortal - part 5 - Better concept details view](#)

References

[1] National Center for Biomedical Ontology. BioPortal. Accessed on February 14th, 2025. Available: <https://bioportal.bioontology.org>.

[2] Noy NF, Shah NH, Whetzel PL, Dai B, Dorf M, Griffith N, et al. BioPortal: ontologies and integrated data resources at the click of a mouse. *Nucleic Acids Res* 2009;37:W170–3. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkp440>.

[3] OntoPortal Alliance. Accessed on February 14th, 2025. Available: <https://ontoportallirmm.org/about/>.